

Transition towards environment friendly consumer products by co-creation of an oxidoreductase foundry

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D7.7 Social Awareness Report

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1 Summary

The OXIPRO project has carried out consumer surveys and awareness-raising activities to explore public attitudes, behaviours, and willingness to pay for biotechnology-based products, taking into account generational and gender differences. Key focus areas included laundering habits, sustainable home textiles, ocean-safe sun care, and the use of marine by-products in food. Findings from surveys, interviews, and data analysis were used to inform online and social media campaigns, open-air outreach, and a round table discussion. Our study has shown that sustainability is becoming an important secondary factor, especially among educated and environmentally conscious consumers. While most consumers are not yet willing to pay more for environmentally friendly products, there is clear potential if these alternatives can match or exceed traditional options in terms of effectiveness and value. The results helped identify knowledge gaps and guided communication efforts around sustainable, enzyme-based innovations.

2 Introduction

Social awareness-raising refers to efforts aimed at increasing public understanding, concern, or engagement with a particular social, environmental, political, or cultural issue. The goal is to inform people, influence attitudes, and often to inspire action or behaviour change.

In addition to the procedures outlined in this report, the measures that were implemented are also partially outlined in Deliverable D1.1 (Stakeholder mapping and stakeholder participation methodology). This report summarizes results from consumer surveys and awareness-raising campaigns, as conducted under WP7, Task 7.4 'social awareness on consumer products of the future' during the 2nd to 4th year (M12-M48) of the project.

Consumer surveys have been conducted to determine habits, perceptions and willingness to pay for biotech products, considering gender and generational differences (ranging from Gen X to Gen Alpha). During the final year, awareness-raising campaigns were implemented to inform and engage future Gen Z consumer groups around specific consumer product developments and innovations in OXIPRO. Focus areas of the surveys included on washing preferences, eco-friendly home textiles, ocean-safe sun care and marine by-products in food. The results of the sector-specific surveys were used as the basis for briefings and other information activities on the benefits of biotechnology. The surveys have been executed to investigate the public's perceptions, attitudes and behaviour in relation to OXIPRO's research approach to developing environmentally friendly products and the growing trend towards enzyme-based technologies. The study included surveys and data analyses to assess the public's understanding of and engagement with these innovations. The aim of the surveys was to identify

knowledge gaps, misconceptions and key factors influencing consumer decision-making, providing valuable insights for trend awareness campaigns, policy recommendations and future marketing strategies.

Online and social media campaigns and open-air campaigns were conducted for targeted dissemination on specific consumer products to GenZ. The results of which are summarised herein. In this context, consumer perceptions and reactions to the innovations targeted by OXIPRO, including biotech-derived products and associated sustainability goals has been analysed.

3 Results

3.1 Consumer behaviour and attitude

Learning about consumers behaviour and attitude towards the OXIPRO in general and the innovation cases in particular are essential within the frame of OXIPRO's mission. Consumers were approached individually or as spokespersons for consumer protection and consumer rights, namely consumer protection organisation.

With online and street surveys consumer attitudes, purchasing behaviour, and preferences regarding detergents, sunscreens, nutraceuticals, and textiles, focusing on sustainability and enzyme-based production were studied. The surveys were conducted either online or on site as street surveys in Berlin (Germany, 2024), Athens (Greece, 2024), and Bergen (Norway, 2025) reaching a diverse age and gender demographic. One-on-one interviews with experts representing consumer protection organisations and individual consumers revealed more detailed insight in specific concerns and attitudes.

Population

Respondents of the surveys and interviewees were of different age and gender, representing the general public. Survey's gender representation is mainly well balanced as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Gender distribution mainly well balanced for all surveys

Consumer’s view on sustainability and environment-friendliness

OXIPRO’s mission is to drive the transition towards environment-friendly and more sustainable consumer products. This mission corresponds well with the attitude of the respondents of our surveys. Sustainability and decreased environmental impact are of importance to more than three-fourth of the respondents. The vast majority is also willing to pay more if more sustainable and environment-friendly produced (see Figure 03). These results were supported by statements of the interviewees. The willingness to consume more sustainable and environment-friendly is widespread, implementation although is hampered by several factors and not yet well translated in daily-life practice.

Figure 2: Consumers care about sustainability and environment-friendliness

Figure 3: Consumers are willing to pay more if products are more sustainable and environment-friendly

Consumer’s view on ingredients and enzymes in particular

Although interested in sustainability and environment-friendliness not all respondents check ingredients before buying a product. Consumers and consumer protection organisation report that the complexity of technical terms in product labels overstrains consumers and interest is generally low for most of the daily-life products. To support consumers in making informed decisions, the Danish consumer protection organisation created the easy-to-use App “Kemiluppen” which provides information and assessment on ingredients according to hazard after scanning the product’s barcode. Interviewees reported that because of the public awareness on sunscreen and its impact on marine ecosystems and skin cancer protection, the interest in ingredients is higher.

Figure 4: No regular ingredient checks before purchase

In general, most respondents do not care if enzymes are used in general and for the innovation cases in particular. Interviews gave some hints on potential worries. Concerns raised over the use of enzymes were the misgivings about possible allergenic potential of remaining enzymes in the product, unknown impact on the skin microbiome, potential misuse of enzymes to fake fish as fresh, sufficient monitoring of the production processes. Because of lack of knowledge enzymes are regarded as suspicious as GMOs.

Figure 5: Most respondents do not care if enzymes are used

3.1.1 Consumer's criteria for purchase

The commitment to a specific brand is generally low for sunscreens and detergents, presenting an opportunity for new or sustainable brands to capture market share.

Figure 6: Brand commitment

Purchase criteria - Sunscreen

When we swim, up to 25% of the sunscreen applied to our skin washes off into the water. Many commercial sun care products contain organic and mineral UV filters that can harm marine ecosystems and enter wastewater treatment systems. These substances have been linked to toxic effects on marine life. This study analysed consumer behaviour, preferences, and attitudes towards sustainable sunscreens, with a focus on formulations using enzyme technology. A large majority (73.2%) use sunscreen reactively or seasonally rather than proactively daily.

Table 1: Sunscreen - Usage

Sunscreen	Daily Use/ included in Day Care	Seasonal Use	Special occasion use	Never use
Usage (n=176)	27,3%	48,3%	21,6 %	2,8%

Figure 7: Sun Protection Factor (SPF) is the most important purchase criterion for sunscreen

Efficacy (SPF, texture, protection duration) dominates decision-making, sustainability criteria remain secondary for this cohort. Half of the respondents do not check ingredients, Interest in enzyme-based production is niche, though there’s openness if environmental benefits are demonstrated.

The study reveals moderate growth prospects and innovative trends within the sunscreen market, particularly driven by consumer demand for multifunctional and eco-friendly products. Despite a scientifically literate audience, daily sunscreen usage remains relatively low, highlighting the need for increased awareness and engagement.

By leveraging insights from consumer preferences and data from Verified Market Reports¹², there seems to be strong potential to integrate enzyme technology into sunscreen formulations to align with

¹ <https://www.businessresearchinsights.com/market-reports/sunscreen-market-118654>

² <https://www.valuemarketresearch.com/report/natural-and-organic-sunscreen-market>

environmental goals and consumer expectations. Enzyme use, while not yet a mainstream concern, can become a differentiator if positioned correctly through education and performance benefits.

To capitalise on these trends, the following strategic approaches should be considered when developing a new sunscreen product:

- **Educational Campaigns:** Increase awareness of the environmental and performance benefits of enzyme-based products through multi-channel outreach. Survey in cohorts with job-related basic knowledge indicate that educational campaigns based on scientific results only might be unrewarding.
- **Product Innovation:** Prioritised development of sunscreens with improved texture, durability, and skin compatibility, while integrating enzyme technology to enhance environmental performance.
- **Pricing Strategy:** Adoption of value-based pricing models that emphasise long-term benefits, such as skin health and ecological impact, rather than competing on cost alone.
- **Brand Reinforcement:** Investing in strong sustainable branding that communicates transparency, innovation, and commitment to eco-conscious values in a dynamic and evolving market landscape.

The focus on innovative formulations and sustainable practices underscores a broader transformation in consumer expectations—presenting both a challenge and a rich opportunity for brands to lead with science-backed, eco-responsible skincare solutions.

Purchase criteria - Detergent

Modern detergents are increasingly designed for low temperature washing (<40°C) to support energy efficiency. However, effective hygienisation at these temperatures can require environmentally harmful ingredients. Effectiveness (cleaning power) remains the primary driver, with smell and cost following closely. Eco-friendliness is important but still ranks just behind sensory and practical factors. Comparable with the sunscreen study, brand-loyalty is low. Consumers are open to switching brands, which presents a strong opportunity for innovation and eco-conscious marketing

Sensory Appeal: Scent is a primary factor at point of purchase; one respondent states: *"The truth is that when I go to a store, I open the detergent and the scent is my first deciding factor for the purchase, although the composition is also key."*

Price Sensitivity: Consumers accept a slight price increase for sustainability, but expectations for affordability remain: *"The price could be a little higher than for the other detergents but not too much."*

Figure 8: Cleaning power is the most important purchase criterion for detergents.

Interviewees raised concerns about the necessity of additional products in the detergent sector. The enormous number of products for any specific type of fabric includes already products allowing low temperature cleaning.

Conclusion

The results of surveys and interviews highlight key trends in detergent consumer behaviour: washing performance, scent, and cost are top decision factors, but eco-consciousness is a major concern, especially in a well-educated, scientifically informed consumer base. The market might yield strong potential for eco-friendly innovation if it meets expectations around efficacy, scent, and affordability. To tap into this evolving market, companies should consider the following strategic directions when developing new detergents:

- **Product Innovation:** Development of high-performing, sustainable detergents with appealing scents and user-friendly textures (particularly liquids).
- **Educational Campaigns:** Information of the consumers about the environmental benefits of sustainable formulations without compromising on performance or price.
- **Value-Based Pricing Strategy:** Highlighting the long-term value of eco-friendly products—both in environmental and household impact.
- **Brand Reinforcement:** Building strong eco-conscious brand identities, appealing to the majority who are not brand-loyal and open to trying new options.

This alignment of performance, sensory appeal, and sustainability can help companies differentiate and succeed in an increasingly value-driven consumer landscape.

Product Usage Patterns

Insight: Across all sectors, consumers show low brand attachment and a clear willingness to pay extra for eco-friendly options. The largest barrier in nutraceuticals is adoption. Due to low numbers of respondents for the nutraceutical the high number of brand loyalty should be assessed carefully.

Table 2: Product Usage Patterns

Category	Regular Users	Brand Loyalty	Willing to Pay More for Sustainability
Sunscreen	Daily use low (27,3%)	Low (24,4%)	79,8% (“yes” or “rather yes”)
Detergents	Universal use	Very low (22,9%)	80,8% (“yes” or “rather yes”)
Nutraceuticals	Low use (32,8%)	High (85,7%)	70% (“yes” or “rather yes”)

Key Purchasing Criteria

Sunscreen:

Top concerns: Sun protection factor (69,3%), price (34,4%), texture (28,8%), eco-friendly (29,5%)

Sensory sensitivity: Texture and scent strongly influence repurchase

Environmental concern: High; 47,4% check ingredients, 49,1% willing to pay more (yes)

Washing Detergents:

Top concerns: Cleaning power (52,8%), cost (35,4%), smell (34%), eco-friendly (36,1%)

Eco-conscious: 75,9% care about sustainability

Preferred format: Liquid (52,1%)

Nutraceuticals:

Top barrier: Lack of use (Usage 32,8%) and knowledge (no knowledge 59,7%)

Sensory aversion: 42,1% deterred by fishy smell

Sustainability-driven: 78,2% care about eco-friendliness

Insight: Consumers prioritise performance first, followed closely by cost and sensory quality (especially texture and smell). Sustainability is a decisive secondary factor that enhances product acceptance— but only if primary needs are met.

Sensory & Ethical Sensitivities

- Texture and scent matter most in personal care and detergents.
- Nutraceuticals face unique barriers like aversion to animal origins and unpleasant odors.

Knowledge & Education Gaps

Insight: Particularly in nutraceuticals, a lack of knowledge is a barrier to ethical purchasing. Across categories, consumer education campaigns represent a key tool to influence purchase intent and brand loyalty.

Cross-category strategic recommendations based on the analysis carried out

Educational Campaigns

- Promote understanding of production processes and environmental impacts.
- Demystify enzymes, eco-formulations and benefits.
- Targeted transparent, data-driven messages to scientific demographics.

Product innovation

- Improve sensory properties: texture, odour, application/use experience.
- Utilise advances in enzyme and biotechnology to develop high performance, sustainable products.
- Preferring odourless alternatives, especially for food supplements.

Value-orientated pricing

- Shift messaging to long-term value and ethical impact rather than unit cost.
- Pricing should be based on efficacy and sustainability, not just green branding.

Brand positioning

- Build an environmentally conscious brand identity.
- Emphasise certifications, transparency of ingredients and traceable sourcing.
- Creation of emotional values (care for health, the planet, the family) as well as product specifications.

3.1.2 Conclusion

Across all three sectors, this educated, and ethically motivated demographic seeks products that work, feel good, and align with environmental values. While functional performance remains paramount, sustainability and sensory quality are powerful differentiators.

It can be expected that brands that invest in eco-conscious innovation, transparency, and education will thrive in this values-driven marketplace.

3.2 Open-Air Campaigns

Open-Air Campaigns are public awareness initiatives held in outdoor spaces such as parks, squares, and university campuses. Designed to engage diverse audiences in visible and interactive ways, these campaigns aimed to foster dialogue and raise awareness of enzyme-based biotechnological innovations within the OXIPRO project. These campaigns have been initiated to foster communication with the public and raise awareness on enzyme-based biotechnological approaches and the OXIPRO innovation cases.

The target group for open-air campaigns were so-called Generation Z and Y, according to Peschl born between 1981-1995 and 1996-2012, respectively³. “In addition, social responsibility, human rights, tolerance, justice, diversity and environmental awareness are very important topics for Generation Z (Ernst & Young GmbH 2020, Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu Limited 2021, Albert et al. 2019). In studies on the values of Generation Y, these aspects are less or hardly at all in focus. Health is very relevant for both generations (Schnetzer 2021). Generation Z in particular is sensitized to health issues such as a healthy lifestyle (mediated by influencers in social media, for example), mental illness and Covid19 at a young age.”³

During these events, OXIPRO early career researchers engaged students through stand activities and informal discussions in high-traffic campus areas. Participants were invited to learn about enzyme-based biotech solutions and complete a shared survey across both locations. In total, over 130 students took part, with each campaign reaching approximately 50–60 individuals. The initiatives successfully connected with the target demographic, combining scientific outreach with meaningful dialogue.

Figure 8. OXIPRO researchers at Booth during campaigns in Barcelona (left) and Bergen University

³ Peschl, A. ifaa — Institut für angewandte Arbeitswissenschaft e. V.

https://www.arbeitswissenschaft.net/fileadmin/Downloads/Angebote_und_Produkte/Zahlen_Daten_Fakten/Factsheet_Generation_Z_final.pdf

The respondents were mainly younger than 25 years old, thus representing the targeted customer group Gen Z (75% in Bergen, 47,9% in Barcelona) and 25-44 years old, representing the target group Gen Y (25% in Bergen, 32,4% in Barcelona), respectively (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Targeting the aimed consumer groups of Gen Y and Gen Z

The vast majority of respondents (97,3%), as expected from Gen Z but not necessarily from Gen Y target group representatives, care about the environment, with 51,1% stating “the environment is very important for me”.

Half of the respondents check ingredients before purchasing at least sometimes (54,3%), in line with the expected attitude to make informed decisions and expect transparency from producers.

Figure 10: Heterogenous knowledge about enzymes in general. Responses to the question ‘Do you know what an enzyme is?’ Differences are due to the cohorts approached. In Barcelona almost only students from Biology and Health or natural science related studies participated.

The knowledge about enzymes differs widely between the two groups studied, which might be related to the favoured discipline stated by the respondents (Figure 10). In Barcelona 71,8% of the

respondents focused on life science/biotechnology/human health, whereas the respondents in Bergen focused on other disciplines with only 12,5% focus life science/biotechnology/human health. This may reflect the nature of the events targeted; the Barcelona event was held at a Biotech Day and would be expected to draw people more familiar with enzymes than the general public. In contrast, the respondents in Bergen were recruited randomly in a University of Bergen common area. This explains why there were many freshmen students and that their fields of study were more heterogenous than in the Barcelona group. Indeed, while only 26.3% of respondents who had studied something other than biology and health knew what an enzyme is, 96.6% of the ones who studied a biology-related field did know. This indicates that there is a lot of room to educate the non-biologist public on the benefits of enzymes.

Figure 11: No general reservations about enzymes in everyday goods

No general reservations about enzymes in detergents or cosmetics have been observed, with 57% of respondents like to have enzymes in these products, but remaining uncertainty in 41% of respondents (Figure 11). This is in line with results from consumer interviews. Interviews revealed general acceptance but also some concerns over the use of enzymes, like i.e. possible allergenic potential of remaining enzymes in the product, unknown impact on the skin microbiome.

Figure 12: Imagine you have the option to buy a sunscreen with the enzyme-made UV filter, which is less harmful to aquatic organisms. How much are you willing to spend for such a bottle of sunscreen?

Figure 13: Imagine you could buy a laundry detergent which is the same smell and quality as the one you usually use but also uses an enzyme technology which enables better hygienisation. How much are you willing to spend for such a bottle of laundry detergent?

The willingness to pay more for more sustainable products due to enzyme use is moderate as depicted with sunscreen and detergents below and differ in both countries (Figures 12 and 13). More respondents in Spain tend to be willing to pay more for more sustainable products in both cases. These results suggest that for future investigations national specialities should be taken specifically into consideration. Although with good intent, the willingness to pay more might be hampered in implementation due probably limited financial resources of the younger target group.

3.2.1 Key Findings:

- A strong interest in sustainability suggests that enzyme-enhanced products are widely accepted, especially among students.
- Respondents showed a willingness to pay extra for greener choices, revealing a growing market

3.3 Online communication campaigns

Online communication campaign on the website and social media was conducted based on and in line with the project's CDP (Deliverables D7.1, D7.2 and D7.3). The communication and dissemination

strategy was designed from the outset to effectively communicate the objectives, results and impacts of OXIPRO to a wide range of stakeholders. A dynamic, multi-channel communication approach has been implemented, including a dedicated project website, an active social media presence, newsletters, scientific publications, stakeholder workshops, policy briefs and public engagement campaigns. Several calls for participation on LinkedIn have been posted to raise awareness and call for contributions.

Figure 14 Call for survey respondents, example 1

The project's external newsletters (152 subscribers) as well as 'the enzyme cluster's own newsletter 'The Active Site' (322 subscribers) were used to recruit survey respondents and to promote awareness on the potential of biotechnology for specific consumer products.

4 Conclusion

As with the surveys, the World Cafes made it clear that although awareness exists, other factors such as social pressure and habits play just as big a role in consumer behaviour as the production and pricing of consumer goods and food. Education is needed to bring about change in a medium and long-term manner. The study highlights a shift in consumer behaviour in areas such as skincare, detergents and dietary supplements, driven by a growing ethical awareness and demand for sustainability without compromising on performance, price or sensory experience. Educated and environmentally conscious consumers are increasingly looking for multifunctional, eco-friendly products, but uptake is hampered by low awareness, unclear labelling and cost barriers.

Strategic opportunities include:

- **Product innovation:** developing high performance, enzyme-based and sustainable solutions with improved ease of use and environmental performance.
- **Educational campaigns:** Raise awareness of the benefits of environmentally friendly products, especially for scientifically literate populations.
- **Value-based pricing:** Position sustainability as a long-term value rather than a premium cost.
- **Brand differentiation:** Build transparent, trustworthy brands with a strong environmentally conscious identity.

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Wider implications:

Cultural change, legislative support and institutional engagement (e.g. universities and employers) are essential to make sustainability the norm. Enzyme technology and circular design are promising, scalable innovations, and systemic efforts in communication, education and infrastructure will be critical to drive behavioural change and market transformation.